

Decoding Places Through the Lens of Urban Vitality: A Multidimensional Analysis of Mobility, Activity, and Economic Factors

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As the world grapples with population growth, global pandemics, and climate change, the landscape of urban development and transportation in cities has been substantially disrupted. In this evolving context, identifying, measuring, and utilizing urban vitality (UV)—a concept proposed by urban planners decades ago—has become increasingly critical. Advances in computing, the proliferation of sensor technologies, and the accessibility of open data portals have significantly shifted our approach to understanding urban environments.

This research proposal delves into the multifaceted concept of urban vitality, distinguishing itself by emphasizing the dynamic perspective of urban movement alongside traditional static features. Therefore, this study introduces an innovative approach to understanding UV from a dynamic perspective and proposes the novel concept of 'mobility vitality (MV)'. This term encapsulates the intensity and diversity of mobility within specific urban areas, reflecting how individuals interact with the environment through transportation and movement. MV reflects how people interact with their environment through varied transportation and movement, offering a unique perspective that contrasts with existing UV measures. These conventional UV methods primarily focus on the volume of active participation or people flow within a specific area, usually by counting individuals present in a location over a certain time. MV, however, emphasizes the dynamics of movement, tracking individuals as they transition between areas, rather than solely focusing on the concentration of activities at the destination. Moreover, unlike previous traffic analyses, which often limit their scope to one or two transport modes, my approach integrates a diversity of transport behaviors, contributing to a more comprehensive view of urban dynamics.

Then, my study expands the scope to include dynamic urban vitality (DUV) and latent urban vitality (LUV), introducing a comprehensive framework that encompasses three dimensions of urban vitality: mobility, activity, and economic vitality. By employing machine learning techniques and advanced statistical algorithms, this chapter aims to investigate the interplay between DUV and LUV, exploring their spatiotemporal distribution and the impact of specific LUV sub-indicators on DUV. It also investigates the alignment of current urban and transportation planning with real-world transportation conditions, exploring the interplay between dynamic transport changes and socio-economic, demographic, and environmental factors.

The methodology proposed in this work not only deepens our understanding of UV but also provides actionable insights for transportation planning and policymaking. Theoretically, it effectively bridges the divide between vitality and mobility research, breaking down the expansive and high-level notion of UV into more detailed and precise components. Practically, this research is pivotal as it contributes to urban development strategies that emphasize tailored transportation planning, promoting convenience, comfort, and equity. The major significance of this work lies in its potential to influence how cities are planned and developed in response to emerging challenges. It underscores the importance of innovative approaches in addressing the dynamic needs of urban areas, thereby shaping more resilient, sustainable, and inclusive urban environments.